

oil (5%) was applied to seedlings 2 h before inoculation.

Increasing the number of insects increased infection from 50 to 95% in susceptible ADT31 and from 5 to 35% in resistant TNAU831520 (see figure). In

ADT31, neem oil significantly reduced infection rates when 1 GLH was used for inoculation. A similar reduction was observed with inoculation using 3 or 5 GLH/plant.

All treated plants of TNAU831520 were free of infection when one GLH was used for inoculation. Neem oil reduced infection to 10% in resistant plants inoculated using 3 or 5 insects. □

Some pathological and physiological diseases of rice in Punjab

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In Punjab, rice is grown as a wet season crop May-Oct. With the release of high-yielding varieties IR8, Jaya, and PR106, the area under rice cultivation has increased from 258,000 ha in 1966-67 to 1,703,000 ha in 1985-86.

Samples of diseased rice plants received for diagnosis by PDC 1980-85 are shown in the table. Bacterial blight appeared in 71% of the samples in 1980, then its incidence declined to 1985, when it increased to 44% samples infected.

Sheath rot has threatened the most

Diseases in samples of rice in Punjab, India, 1980-85.

Disease	Diseased samples (%)					
	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985
Bacterial blight	71	28	13	10	10	44
Sheath rot	3	19	19	27	6	2
False smut	5	1	5	8	7	2
Sheath blight	4	7	5	3	3	1
Bacterial leaf streak	3	0	0	0	0	4
Acid rain	0	0	0	0	1	2
Zn deficiency	13	17	50	28	10	8
Fe deficiency	0	6	0	15	5	4
N deficiency	0	16	3	8	8	3

popular variety PR106. False smut has recently gained importance, with infection in 1-7.5% of the samples. Stem rot caused by *Sclerotium oryzae*, considered to be very severe before the introduction of high-yielding varieties,

was conspicuously absent from the samples received. This could be due to rice - wheat rotation. Bacterial leaf streak appeared occasionally in 1980 and 1985. Blast and brown leaf spot seem unimportant now. □

Pest Control and Management INSECTS

Antifeedant effect of sublethal levels of carbofuran against whitebacked planthopper (WBPH)

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We evaluated the antifeedant effect of sublethal levels of systemic insecticide carbofuran against WBPH *Sogatella furcifera* (Horvath). Three treatments were tested: topically treating WBPH with carbofuran solutions in acetone, using a no-soil root-zone application to susceptible glasshouse-grown TN1 rice plants, and treating leaves of potted TN1 plants with acetone solutions using a fine brush. Recently emerged (3-5 d)

Table 1. Antifeeding effect of carbofuran on macropterous WBPH females.^a Newcastle upon Tyne, United Kingdom.

Treatment method	Concentration	Quantity of amino acids in honeydew ^b (µg dry weight/female per 24 h)	Antifeeding response (%)
Leaf (µg/cm ²)	0.159	28.6 a	54.7
	0.079	33.7 a	46.9
	0.016	43.8 b	31.3
	0.0	63.9 c	
Topical (ng/female)	0.1	23.3 a	78.1
	0.02	34.5 a	67.6
	0.01	54.1 b	48.6
	0.002	77.9 c	25.7
	0.0	105.6 d	
Root zone (µM)	2.0	18.5 a	68.4
	1.5	23.0 b	59.7
	1.0	30.9 c	47.4
	0.5	36.2 d	36.8
	0.1	46.9 e	17.5
	0.0	56.8 f	

^a Within a treatment method, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at P = 0.05 by Duncan's multiple range test. No mortality was observed with any concentration (i.e., less than 5% mortality). Temperature 26 ± 1°. ^b Mean of 3 replications: quantity of amino acids in honeydew measured colorimetrically using glutamic acid as standard.